

Deliverable D4.3

User Portal live cataloguing data within the GDI

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable is led by Task T4.1, and details the design, development, and deployment of the User Portal within the Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI), enabling live cataloguing of datasets and secure, standards-based data discovery in a federated ecosystem.

Key technical achievements include:

- Integration with FAIR Data Point (FDP) for metadata-level dataset discovery, aligned with FAIR principles.
- Adoption of DCAT-AP 3.0 and draft HealthDCAT-AP for health-specific metadata profiles.
- Implementation of dataset access request workflows via the Resource Entitlement Management System (REMS).
- Record-level dataset discovery via the Beacon Network for federated genomic queries
- Development of open-source metadata tooling, including Semantic Models Pydantic RDF Ontology (SemPyRO) and Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL), for onboarding and validation.
- Enhanced platform operations (CI/CD, OpenTelemetry, vulnerability scanning, license compliance checks).

A staging environment has been deployed in collaboration with Work Package 3 (WP3), integrated with the Life Science Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (LS-AAI) and REMS. The User Portal's full functionality was successfully demonstrated in Milestones MS7, MS8, and MS11.

Despite pending legal establishment of the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC), the User Portal is technically ready for being operated in production. Major ongoing development of core interoperability components, like a GDI-specific data model for Beacon queries, and the final version of HealthDCAT-AP, will require further development, but do not pose operational impediments.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'. For more details of project outcomes, see [here](#)]

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers</p>	Yes

(e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.	
<p>Outcome 5</p> <p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	No

3. Methods

This deliverable documents the work undertaken by WP4 Task 4.1 to develop and deploy the User Portal within the GDI ecosystem. Additionally, the work includes documentation, security measures, deployment procedures, and compliance with Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) licenses.

The Task 4.1 is closely linked to several Work Packages (WPs). WP2 (Pillar I - Long-Term Sustainability) provides Data Protection by Design and by Default principles. WP3 (Pillar II - Deployment of 1+MG national nodes) focuses on the technical implementation and deployment of national nodes. This WP also standardizes data flows, authentication mechanisms, and monitoring, aligning the User Portal with national infrastructures. Lastly, WP7 (Pillar III - Use Cases) provides meaningful use cases, used for demonstration of the User Portal.

Given the complexity of interacting with national nodes and implementing 1+MG requirements, the WP4 Task 4.1 followed an open development approach with frequent releases, and continuous engagement with other work packages. That includes Cross-pillar, Pillar II, and WP4 monthly meetings, Task 4.1 is also involved in WP3 monthly meetings, and in Product Owners monthly meetings. To ensure understanding of the 1+MG framework and data protection by design and default principles, we also frequently engage with WP2 (Pillar I).

4. Description of work accomplished

The User Portal has undergone significant development and enhancement after Milestone 11¹, delivered on 16 January 2024. Since then, we integrated the User Portal with LS-AAI²; we integrated the User Portal with Beacon Network³ for querying on Record-level data⁴ and for querying on Allele Frequency⁵. We also integrated it with REMS⁶.

The User Portal supports DCAT-AP 3. This technology choice allows future compatibility with the EHDS metadata model (based on HealthDCAT-AP) with minimum adaptation. . To facilitate integration into the User Portal from National Coordination Points using different profiles, we also provide reference tools and documentation to assist with metadata standardization across infrastructures, using FAIR Data Point (FDP) protocol⁷.

We deployed a staging environment for testing the integration with national nodes. That includes all User Portal components, Keycloak⁸ integrated with LS-AAI as an Identity Provider, and REMS. Beacon Networks are deployed and operated by Centre for Genomic Regulation⁹ (CRG).

The User Portal is composed by the following components:

- The frontend¹⁰, developed in Next.js¹¹. It is responsible for providing a seamless user experience, following the GDI palette.
- API Gateway, developed in Kong¹². It is responsible to centralize API calls from different microservices..
- Dataset Discovery Service¹³, developed in Quarkus¹⁴. It is responsible to integrate with REMS, and abstract data user actions to the frontend.
- Access Management Service¹⁵, developed in Quarkus. It is responsible to integrate with Beacon Network and CKAN, and abstract data user actions to the frontend.

¹ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ZWedrw8EN25Mw10lCQ2Ow73RnAmUhNx0/view>

² <https://lifescience-ri.eu/home.html>

³ <https://docs.genomebeacons.org/networks/>

⁴ <https://beacon-network-backend-demo.ega-archive.org/beacon-network>

⁵ <https://af-gdi-bn-api-demo.ega-archive.org/beacon-network>

⁶ <https://github.com/CSCfi/remS>

⁷ <https://specs.fairdatapoint.org/fdp-specs-v1.2.html>

⁸ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

⁹ <https://www.crg.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/gdi-userportal-frontend>

¹¹ <https://nextjs.org/>

¹² <http://konghq.com/>

¹³ <https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/gdi-userportal-dataset-discovery-service>

¹⁴ <https://quarkus.io/>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/gdi-userportal-access-management-service>

- CKAN Metadata Catalogue¹⁶, developed in CKAN, response to harvest and store GDI nodes' metadata.
- REMS synchronizer¹⁷, developed in Python. It is responsible for synchronizing Metadata Catalogue and REMS.

Please refer to Figure 1, which describes the current technology platform.

Figure 1: Current Solution Architecture View

In Figure 2 below, one has a view of the components deployed per application component.

¹⁶ <https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/gdi-userportal-ckan-docker>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/gdi-userportal-rems-synchronizer>

Figure 2: Components Diagram

In Figures 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7, it is possible to see all use cases the User Portal implements.

Figure 3: Use Case Diagram on Metadata-level query

Figure 4: Use Case Diagram on Application Submission

Figure 4: Use Case Diagram on Dataset Onboarding

Figure 6: Use Case Diagram on Record-level query

Figure 7: Use Case Diagram on Allele frequency query

For additional details on the User Portal architecture, please refer to the documentation¹⁸.

Recent work also included implementation of observability, and improvements on error handling, security, automation, enhancements on metadata management, and extending the documentation.

In the following sections we detailed each aspect of the work undertaken for D4.3.

4.1 Development

To support the implementation of the 1+MG framework, we integrated the User Portal with REMS, from dataset selection, to application creation, form validation and application submission.

In Figure 8, the data user can see the Datasets page with a search bar and filtering options. This page displays two categories: one based on DCAT-AP metadata fields, and one based on the GDI metadata model.

¹⁸ <https://genomicdatainfrastructure.github.io/gdi-userportal-docs/>

Figure 8: Datasets page

Beacon Query was integrated into existing dataset discovery capabilities. In Figure 9, we display both DCAT-AP 3 filters and genomic filters after the data user is logged-in — e.g. Diseases, treatment, and intervention.

Figure 9: Datasets page including metadata, phenotypic and genomic filters

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In Figure 10, the data user can see the basket with all selected datasets. From that view the data user can either request access, when clicking on "Request Now", or go back to datasets page, when clicking on "Continue adding".

European Genomic Data Infrastructure

Home Datasets G-Variants Themes Publishers About

Shopping cart icon 1 BPLS

Your Basket (1)

Continue adding Request now

GDI-LU-D-T0001
Colorectal cancer dataset

Created on 1 November 2024 Modified on 1 November 2024 24 Distributions

Remove from basket

How to use the data portal →

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Legal
 Terms & Conditions
 Privacy Notice
 Cookie Policy

Portal Links
 Datasets
 Themes
 Publishers
 About

Contact Us

 gdi-coordination@elixir-europe.org

Figure 10: Basket view

Once clicking on "Request now", the data user will be redirected to the newly created application, illustrated by Figure 11. In that page, the data user must fulfill the application form accordingly, accept Terms & Conditions, if any available. The data user can also invite a new participant to join, clicking on "Add Participant". Data users may also delete applications if created in error, or submit.

Figure 11: Application form

While Figure 5 illustrates the form used during Milestone 7 and Milestone 8 demonstrations, the User Portal supports the following field types provided by REMS:

- Header: textual form entry for highlighting or titling parts of the application.
- Label: textual form entry for highlighting or clarifying parts of the application.
- Text field: Short text input.
- Text Area: Long text input.
- Option list: dropdown list of options, where only one element can be selected.
- Multi-select list: multiple checkboxes that can be selected.
- Table: tabular content input, where every cell is a short text input.
- Date field: date without time input.
- Email: short text input with email format validation.
- Phone number: short text input with phone format validation.
- Attachment: file upload input.

Figure 12 below shows a form with all supported field types.

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Application 2025/17 DRAFT

Last Event: created at 7 April 2025, 16:46 (CEST)

Delete
Submit

Complete Form

This is a header, it can be used to break the form into multiple sections

This is a label. It can be used to add text in the form, for any purpose - e.g. clarifying a section.

Text Field

Text Area

Text Area

Option List

Select an option
▼

Multi-select List

Option 1

Option 2

Table Add Row

Column 1	Column 2

Date Field

Email Address

Phone number

▼

Attachment Upload File

Datasets

GDI-LU-D-T0001

Participants

bruno.pacheco

Add Participant

Events

created
at 7 April 2025, 16:46 (CEST)

Terms & Conditions

General Terms of Use

License text in English. License text in English...

Not Accepted

Accept All

Figure 12: All field types included in a application form

When clicking on "Submit", the application is validated to ensure the data user is compliant to the workflow configuration. That means:

- all mandatory fields must be fulfilled.
- the content of the form must be valid — e.g. email fields must respect email format.
- All applicable Terms & Conditions must be accepted.

If not, as can be seen in Figure 13 below, messages are displayed in the form, to highlight existing problems with the form.

The application could not be submitted.

Application 2025/12 DRAFT Delete Submit

Last Event: created at 7 April 2025, 14:56 (CEST)

DARREV 1.0

Ethics Approval Upload File
This field is required

Project Description Upload File
This field is required

Data Analysis Plan Upload File
This field is required

Funding Source (Optional) Upload File

Peer Review Upload File
This field is required

Datasets
COVID-19 dataset of aggregated data.

Participants
bruno.pacheco
Add Participant

Events
created at 7 April 2025, 14:56 (CEST)

Terms & Conditions
No terms and conditions have been defined.

Figure 13: Application form with error messages

After submission, the data user can list their previously created applications. For that, the data user must click on the “Directory” icon in the top-right corner, beside their initials. Refer to Figure 14, below.

European Genomic Data Infrastructure | Home | Datasets | Allele Frequency | Themes | Publishers | About |

APPLICATIONS | ENTITLEMENTS

Manage your Applications
View and update your submitted applications

Status	Application ID	Created	Modified	Dataset
DRAFT	2025/12	Created on 7 April 2025	Modified on 7 April 2025	COVID-19 dataset of aggregated data.
SUBMITTED	2025/10	Created on 21 March 2025	Modified on 21 March 2025	GDI-LU-D-T0001

Figure 14: Applications list

After submitting an application, the data user will receive a notification via email stating the action, as can be seen on Figure 15. All status change notifications are sent to the data user.

- Your application 2025/10 has been submitted

Figure 15: Notification on status change

Data users can also list their entitlements — datasets to which they were granted access — as illustrated by Figure 16. Clicking on the “Directory” icon in the top-right corner, then on “Entitlements”, the data user is able to see when the entitlement is valid by comparing “Start” and “End” dates against the current date.

Figure 16: List of datasets which the data user was granted access to

The data user can also query on allele frequency, clicking on “Allele Frequency” — displayed in the menu on the top of the page. Refer to Figure 17 below.

European Genomic Data Infrastructure

Home Datasets Allele Frequency Themes Publishers About

Search for your variant:

Variant: 3-45864731-T-C Ref Genome: GRCh37 Cohort: All

Variant Example: 3-45864731-T-C

Dataset	Population	Allele Count	Allele Number	Homozygous	Heterozygous	Frequency
Beacon: org.ega-archive.beacon-af-gdi-spain						
COVID_pop11_fin_2	FINLAND	6536	84092	528	6008	0.0777
Beacon: org.nbis.ga4gh-approval-beacon-test						
COVID_pop11_fin_1	FINLAND	6959	82998	580	6379	0.0838
Beacon: pt.biodata.gdi.beacon-alleles						
COVID_pop12_ita_1	ITALY	6818	83028	600	6218	0.0675

Figure 17: Allele Frequency page

Metadata onboarding and standardization efforts have led to the development of dedicated tools and documentation, leveraging existing open-source solutions like FDP and CKAN¹⁹ to streamline the process and avoid reinventing the wheel.

While CKAN provides basic DCAT²⁰ metadata support, enhancements were made to support DCAT-AP³²¹ and HealthDCAT-AP²² — until the publication of this deliverable, HealthDCAT-AP is in draft mode. This work included upstream contributions to the open-source CKAN DCAT²³ extension further enhancing HealthDCAT-AP support, aligning it with European Health Data Space (EHDS) requirements. Additionally, new open-source CKAN extension for FDP²⁴ was developed..

FDP was chosen to ensure "FAIR data at the source," simplifying metadata onboarding. SHACLs²⁵ define metadata structures and validate input, and their extension now supports HealthDCAT-AP metadata. To facilitate user adoption, the Semantic Models Pydantic RDF Ontology²⁶ (SemPyRO) Python package was developed, to provide a structured and user-friendly way to onboard metadata into FDP via Jupyter Notebooks.

¹⁹ <https://ckan.org/>

²⁰ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

²¹ <https://semiceu.github.io/DCAT-AP/releases/3.0.0/>

²² <https://healthdcat-ap.github.io/>

²³ <https://github.com/ckan/ckanext-dcat>

²⁴ <https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/gdi-userportal-ckanext-fairdatapoint>

²⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/>

²⁶ <https://github.com/Health-RI/SeMPyRO>

Additionally, SemPyRO can transform existing data formats into DCAT, such as from CSV files or metadata exported from data management tools. This is particularly useful for institutions that already manage their datasets in internal systems — SeMPyRO helps map those structures into the required DCAT format, reducing manual effort and being compliant with the standard.

On Figure 18, one can have a look at the FDP catalogue page.

The screenshot shows the FAIR Data Point interface. At the top, there is a search bar and a user profile icon labeled 'AE'. The main content area is titled 'My FAIR Data Point' and includes a description of the data point, a list of catalogs (currently showing 'GDI Health-ri catalog'), and a list of metadata fields such as 'Conforms to', 'Metadata modified', 'Metadata issued', 'Metadata identifier', 'Title', 'Publisher', 'License', 'Language', 'End point url', and 'Description'. The 'Description' field contains the text: 'Duis pellentesque, nunc a fringilla varius, magna dui porta quam, nec ultricies augue turpis sed velit. Donec id consectetur ligula. Suspendisse pharetra egestas massa, vel varius leo viverra at. Donec scelerisque id ipsum id semper. Maecenas facilisis augue vel justo molestie aliquet. Maecenas sed mattis lacus, sed viverra risus. Donec iaculis quis lacus vitae scelerisque. Nullam fermentum lectus nisi, id vulputate nisi congue nec. Morbi fermentum justo at justo bibendum, at tempus ipsum tempor. Donec facilisis nibh sed lectus blandit venenatis. Cras ullamcorper, justo vitae feugiat commodo, orci metus suscipit purus, quis sagittis turpis ante eget ex. Pellentesque malesuada a metus eu pulvinar. Morbi rutrum euismod eros at varius. Duis finibus dapibus ex, a hendrerit mauris efficitur at.'

Figure 18: HealthRI FDP page

4.2 Operations

The work on the deployment side complemented new developments, focusing on enhancing the system's reliability, maintainability and observability. Prior to the D4.3, the User Portal has been running only in the development environment²⁷.

We agreed with WP3 that a staging environment²⁸ will be deployed for simulating a production-like infrastructure, and use it as a demonstrator for the Data Governance processes, defined by 1+MG. We will create and publish the staging environment by 30 April 2025. We agreed with LS-AAI that the

²⁷ <https://portal.dev.gdi.lu/>

²⁸ <https://portal.staging.gdi.lu/>

staging environment will remain in testing mode until we have a production environment available. CRG will deploy a staging infrastructure for Beacon Networks by the end of the 3rd quarter of 2025.

To support troubleshooting and monitor the User Portal activities, we are deploying a centralized logging system, based on Open Telemetry²⁹. Logs and traces are produced by the applications and stored in OpenObserve³⁰ and Dozzle³¹. OpenObserve is registering only unexpected errors, and tracing requests within the User Portal stack. The tracing can be easily expanded to other external services, namely Beacon Network, if they implement the same standards.

Quality, security, compliance, and vulnerability controls were strengthened through the adoption of robust CI/CD pipelines. That includes static code analysis with prettiers, linters, REUSE³² and Sonar Cloud³³, and docker container scanning with Trivy³⁴. That pipeline is illustrated by Figure 19.

Figure 19: CI/CD screenshot

On Figure 20, one can see a SonarCloud dashboard, displaying quality gates as well as various quality and security metrics.

²⁹ <https://opentelemetry.io/>

³⁰ <https://openobserve.ai/>

³¹ <https://dozzle.dev/>

³² <https://reuse.software/>

³³ <https://www.sonarsource.com/products/sonarcloud/>

³⁴ <https://trivy.dev/latest/>

Figure 20: Sonar Cloud dashboard

We also use Snyk.io³⁵ for continuous vulnerability management. In figure 21, which can be seen below, it is possible to see a dashboard with all User Portal components, sorted by the number of vulnerabilities.

Figure 21: Snyk dashboard

³⁵ <https://snyk.io/>

We use OSS Review Toolkit³⁶ (ORT) to control if Third-party libraries' licenses are compatible with Apache 2.0³⁷, the default license for User Portal components. Please have a look at Figure 22, where we display the ORT dashboard, with an overview of licenses from all third-party libraries.

Figure 22: ORT dashboard

We have also integrated Renovate³⁸ into our CI/CD pipelines, to ensure we are always aware of the latest versions of all third-party dependencies. Renovate automatically opens pull requests to integrate version changes into the code. In Figure 23, one can see an example of pull request.

Figure 23: Example of pull request opened by Renovate

³⁶ <https://github.com/oss-review-toolkit/ort>

³⁷ <https://spdx.org/licenses/Apache-2.0.html>

³⁸ <https://www.mend.io/renovate/>

To increase quality and security on our code base, we integrated Sourcery³⁹ into the CI/CD pipeline. Sourcery automatically updates the pull request description and adds comments on a variety of aspects, including security, testing, and complexity. In Figure 24, one can see comments from Sourcery in a pull request.


```
.github/workflows/release.yml
Comment on lines +8 to +13
 8 + workflow_dispatch:
 9 +   inputs:
10 +     version:
11 +       description: 'Version increment (major, minor, patch)'
12 +       required: true
13 +       default: 'patch'
```

sourcery-ai bot 3 days ago

suggestion: Consider validating allowed values for version input.

Since the input controls the version bump (major, minor, patch), adding a validation or providing allowed value options may help prevent typos or misconfiguration when manually triggering the workflow.

Suggested change

```
 8 - workflow_dispatch:
 9 -   inputs:
10 -     version:
11 -       description: 'Version increment (major, minor, patch)'
12 -       required: true
13 -       default: 'patch'
```

Figure 24: Sourcery comment in a pull request

³⁹ <https://sourcery.ai/>

5. Results

- Delivered metadata-level dataset discovery using FAIR Data Point (FDP), supporting DCAT-AP 3.0 and draft HealthDCAT-AP profiles.
- Integrated REMS into the User Portal, enabling dataset selection, application creation, validation, and submission.
- Delivered record-data level discovery via Beacon Network for Subject-level data.
- Delivered aggregated level discovery via Beacon Network for Allele Frequency.
- Deployed a staging environment simulating production infrastructure, including integration with LS-AAI and REMS.
- Developed and published SemPyRO, a Python tool for metadata onboarding, DCAT transformation, and SHACL validation.
- Contributed improvements to CKAN's DCAT extension to support HealthDCAT-AP and developed a new CKAN FDP extension.
- Enhanced observability and security via centralized logging via OpenTelemetry
- Vulnerability scanning with SonarCloud, Trivy, and Snyk.
- License compliance checks with ORT.
- Code quality checks with SonarCloud and Sourcery.
- Automated dependency updates with Renovate.
- Demonstrated full User Portal functionality in Milestones MS7 and MS8.

6. Discussion

- The Genomic EDIC legal entity is not yet operational, resulting in delays in governance and production deployment.
- The data model for Beacon queries under the GDI initiative is still under development and remains unfinalized.
- HealthDCAT-AP is currently in draft form; its final implementation may require future alignment efforts.
- The Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) framework has not been implemented, leaving user roles and access policies undefined.
- Inflexible REMS email templates and URL configurations are negatively affecting communication quality.
- Our current environment shows a clear misalignment in identity management across platforms, and LS-AAI adoption remains inconsistent. To address these challenges, we have deployed Keycloak as an intermediary to centralize and streamline user management. This approach not only standardizes our identity management practices but also enhances security and usability.
- With the User Portal, Beacon Networks, and LS-AAI operated by different organizations, formalizing SLAs is essential to mitigate risks related to system availability and reliability.
- The partial automation of the software release pipeline hampers reproducibility and overall efficiency.
- There is currently no mechanism in place for decommissioning datasets that are outdated or have been withdrawn.
- The integration of use conditions into metadata and access request processes has not yet been achieved.
- Update frequency and metadata freshness are undefined and not enforced consistently across national nodes.
- There is a need to establish controlled vocabularies and align ontologies during the metadata onboarding process.
- A help desk channel for supporting data users during the access request process is currently lacking.

7. Conclusions & Impact

- The User Portal is in a production-ready state from a purely technical perspective. Core features — metadata-level discovery, record-level queries, and robust access workflows — have been implemented and validated through synthetic data scenarios. These features align closely with the project's mission to enable seamless, standards-aligned data exchange across national nodes.
- Metadata tooling — e.g., SemPyRO, SHACL, CKAN extensions — significantly lowers the barrier for national nodes and other data contributors to onboard their datasets.
- The introduction of comprehensive CI/CD pipelines, vulnerability scanning, and centralized observability demonstrates a mature operational environment. This focus on security, license compliance, and monitoring ensures that when the Portal transitions into production, it will do so on a solid, maintainable, and auditable footing.
- Collaboration with WP3 on a staging environment paves the way for ongoing iterative testing, promoting reliability and faster response times for any technical issues.
- Legal, governance, and operational frameworks remain a key dependence for real data access and production use.
- Impact is currently limited to demonstrations and testing due to pending operational ownership by Genomic EDIC.

8. Next steps

- Finalize and publish a metadata entry wizard for FDP to support user-friendly onboarding.
- Refine SHACL structures to fully align with GDI Metadata V1.
- Expand the SemPyRO tooling to reflect GDI Metadata V1 and support transformation from common formats to DCAT.
- Integrate Ethical, Legal, Societal Implications (ELSI) metadata elements into dataset descriptions.
- Develop and publish Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for metadata onboarding in FDP.
- Implement decommissioning process for outdated datasets.
- Enable use conditions for datasets.
- Implement unified ontology and term usage across metadata fields.
- Fully automate the software release pipeline, including changelog generation, versioning, and deployment to test and production environments.
- Finalize and document observability tooling.
- Prepare user guides.
- Define and implement RBAC, including role definitions and access policies for data users.
- Align with WP3 integration, metadata harvesting, and data access policies for national nodes in operation.
- Continue engagement with LS-AAI and Beacon Network to establish reliable SLAs for production use.
- Implement harmonised GDI minimal data model from T8.2.
- Implement a minimum integration with Federated Computation Dashboard.
- Implement notification system within User Portal.
- Reduce the scope of beacon queries based on pre-selected DCAT-AP metadata.
- Implement Terms and Conditions for querying Beacon Network
- Implement a help desk to data users.

9. References

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